

THE IMAGE OF DAWN IN THE LYRICS OF RAUF PARFI

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Abstract: This article presents the various meanings of Rauf Parfi's image of dawn, the most beautiful phenomenon of nature. The expression of this symbol in its own and figurative meanings increased the artistic level of the poet's lyrics.

Key words: dawn, poetic purpose, innovation, lyric, revitalization, simile, symbol, image, etc.

Rauf Parfi's personality and poetry are extremely unique and attractive. He is a humble man and a dervish, a painstaking and a poor man, a master and a wise man, a truthful and brave creator. The poet uses various artistic images and images to express his poetic thought. In the poet's lyrics, the images are based on artistry and vitality. About Rauf Parfi's lyrics, Vafo Faizullo says : "His poetry has a rich word, a new and different tone, symbolism and signs, different found rhythms and paces, layers of thoughts and feelings, open and representative of the bitterest and greatest truths. the principle is extraordinary". That's why Rauf Parfi's lyrics are still in the center of attention of readers.

The well-known literary critic D. Kuronov writes about artistic image : "Artistic image is a form of thinking in literature and art, a means of artistic perception of the world and man, a general category of art." In particular, the artist effectively and appropriately uses the image of the moon, which is a celestial body, in poetically describing various scenes and various meanings. Below we tried to analyze the image of the morning in the poet's work.

A constant companion of the lyrical hero. He has been sitting by the river since morning. It is not easy to come to an opinion, of course. If this idea is related to the artist's psyche and world, the images of the river, dawn and sun served to reveal Rauf Parfi's artistic intention:

Tong sahardan o'ltiribsan daryo bo'yida,
Bir fikrga kelmadimgi? Ayt.Ayt.
Yo'qsa kech bo'ladi, quyosh so'nadi hozir.

A symbol that awakens the soul and the body. The lyricist slowly wakes up next to the hero. Dawn draws the hero's attention with her white shawl:

Meni asta uyg'otding kelib,
Ko'zim tushdi oq ro'mollingga ...

It's a gloomy morning. This is where the source of inspiration for artists is revealed. Laylo was precious to Rauf Parfi. If he is not around, the poet is restless. Laylo's absence can be seen in these verses:

G'ira-shira tong. Kimdir kelar,
Laylo, ehtimol.

The lyrical hero deprived himself of sleep at night. He is worried about something or looking for something. He expressed his reception of the morning in poetic verses:

Uyqu bo'lmas menga bugun ham,
Tongni kutib olurman hali...

Beautiful similes and animations abound in the nature lyrics. In the poetry of Rauf Parfi, these artistic images are of special importance. In particular, he showed his artistic poetic skill in expressing the image of the image of the dawn:

Tongda erib ketdi
Kecha.
Uyqusini quvib ko'chaning
Avtolar shovqin solib kechar.

There are words in the world that are pure and beautiful like the morning. Beautiful as a bud opened at dawn, pure as dew on a bud. Everyone is wondering what the word is?! Symbols such as dawn, dew, bud increased the level of artistic image of the band:

Bir so'z bor
Beg'ubor tong kabi go'zal,
Tong chog'i ochilgan g'uncha kabi,
G'unchada shabnam kabi musaffo.

An image that bears witness to the sweet moment of lovers. The artist tells his mother that he will leave early in the morning, that sleep is alien to his parents' eyes, and that he will not be upset about this situation:

Uxlamasdan tonggacha, ona,
Tongda chiqar yorim begumon.
Ko'zingizga uyqu begona,
Mendan xafa bo'lmang, onajon!

The dawn is so beautiful that every morning is different. The lyrical hero describes the morning as beautiful and compares its gray state to his own hair:

Mana, tong. Tonglarning go'zali,
tong oqardi va sochim mening...

Sometimes the enemy on the horse of darkness crowns nature. At this moment, the world goes to sleep reluctantly. And the poor morning can't sleep, maybe he's worried:

Zulmat otli shoh kiymoqda toj,
O'z hukmiga olganda uyqu
Uxlab olar olam noiloj.
Bechora tong-uxlolmaydi u.

Night and morning are opposite images. They never met. The poet used the phrase "wine of the morning" and decorated the verses with artistic decoration:

Kechalarning kechalik yodi
Asta tongning mayidan ichar...

A lighted lamp sings at night. Listen to him, bow to him, exclaims the creator. Until the sun takes its turn, the lamp sings until dawn. Dawn is used in this clause in its meaning:

Chiroqni tinglasangiz, odamlar,
Qarshisida egib turing bosh.
Sizni kuylar u tongga qadar,
Va navbatni olguncha quyosh,
Chiroqni tinglasangiz, odamlar...

"This poem contains a novel meaning, history, drama and tragedies. Man is responsible for whom he bows down to, he is commanded, it is instilled in his mind. First of all, in front of God, divine truths, Mother and Motherland, love."

Dawn is a symbol that informs about the situation of the time. Because in these verses of the creator, the turmoil and anxiety of the time was clearly demonstrated. The turning of the sun into a cannon, and the shooting of arrows at dawn, indicate the unrest of the country:

Tong otmoqda, tong o'qlar otar,
Tong otmoqda, quyosh-zambarak.
Yaralangan Yer shari yotar,
Boshlarida yashil zambarak.

The well-known theoretician scientist Ilhom Ganiyev in his book called "The World of Rauf Parfi Ozturk" analyzed the poem beginning with "Dawn is breaking..." as follows: "Dawn, light, light, goodness; conqueror of darkness and ignorance-night, peace, tranquility, peace of mind, well-being. It is necessary for the whole world - people, plants, animals, from the particle to the universe.

The "green belt" at the beginning of the earth is mother nature, homelands, nations, and all life. But no matter what happens, the fighting people are hopeful for the future, there is still power against ignorance and tyranny in their hearts, it is enough, only the human being should recognize his intelligence, that's the only problem. "

Nights are sometimes sad. Sometimes dark nights do not dawn. It also depends on the situation of the period. The artist also tried to reveal the image of his time:

Yiroq-yiroqlarga cho'zilgan armon,
Qora kechalarning tongi otmagan...

It is a miracle that a small baby sleeps in the morning. The artist skillfully describes the sweet sleep of a baby in the early morning. Perhaps the morning also refers to the baby sleeping in the lap:

Shirin uxlar tong chog'i go'dak,
Uxlar go'dak yo tong ko'ksida.
Yoki go'dak quchog'ida tong,
Uxlar shirin ham tinch, osuda.

Ilhom Ganiyev analyzes this poem as follows: "It is possible that someone or something disturbs the baby who is sleeping sweetly in the morning. The great dream that the world would be as peaceful, clean and peaceful as this baby's sleep is embedded in the lines. Look, the baby is sleeping sweetly in the bosom of an ordinary morning, clean, clear air, bright morning, not inside, but in his "bosom" - his heart, his heart. In this poem, there is a hint that the early morning of mankind, the future, progress, peace, peace of mind, the country, and the nation depend on him .

Dawn is a miracle that inspires humanity to live and gives hope. Rauf Parfi expresses in poetic verses that the people of the whole world hold their hearts to the morning, that they are born for this unrepeatable morning, and that they die for this morning:

Tong otmoqda, musaffo tongga
Yuragini tutar odamlar.
Shu tong uchun kelgan jahonga
Va shu tong deb o'tar odamlar.
Tong otmoqda...

"For this purpose, early in the morning, for the sake of creativity, every day in the morning, man turns his heart to the light, the sun - the miracle of Truth and guidance. Originally, human beings came to this world for the pleasure of living, for self-realization, to know the truth, to

know the real essence, to leave descendants. "And people who call it morning!" This poem summarizes the restlessness and anxiety of the whole human being, living in doubt every morning and every day. "

Most of Rauf Parfi's lyrics are poems dedicated to the image of nature. In particular, we analyzed the different meanings of the symbol of dawn. In the analyzed part, the image of dawn is used in its own and figurative meanings, embodying the inner feelings of the lyrical hero, the situation of the era and time, the sum of sorrow and pain. It is understood in the poems of the poet that the dawn is a constant companion and companion of the creator. Ilhom Ganiyev writes about the lyrical art of Rauf Parfi: "If we summarize Rauf Parfi Ozturk's literary-aesthetic views on poetry and poetry, we can see this conditional ranking: WORD, POETRY, WILL, HUMAN, FAITH, COUNTRY, NATION, TRUTH, FREEDOM AND UNITY OF TURKEY, HUMANITY, STRUGGLE . In fact, these qualities are glorified and sung in the essence of all of the artist's poems dedicated to the image of nature, sometimes philosophical and socio-political.

In short, the image of dawn appears in each poem with its new meaning. This situation indicates the high artistic skill of the creator. That is why the samples of the poet's work are still in the center of attention of readers.

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